

Stručni rad

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VODOMERI ZA HLADNU VODU – NASLEĐENA PRAKSA OVERAVANJA VODOMERA I MOGUĆNOSTI USKLAĐIVANJA SA NOVOM ZAKONSKOM REGULATIVOM

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Rezime:

U radu su prikazane aktivnosti UTVSI vezane za primenu Pravilnika o overavanju vodomera koji su predviđeni za upotrebu u domaćinstvu, poslovnom prostoru i lakoj industriji, koji je u primeni od 1.1.2026. godine. Analizirano je stanje vanrednog overavanja vodomera koji su u upotrebi u JKP ViK, uz razna ograničenja i prepreke za striktno sprovođenje zakonske regulative. Cilj je da se kroz analizu realnog stanja dođe do prihvatljivih rešenja, uz poštovanje propisa, kako za JKP ViK, tako i za Direkciju za mere i dragocene metale - organa uprave nadležnog za poslove metrologije i nadzor nad primenom Zakona o metrologiji. Kroz pregled stanja vodomera u više JKP ViK, imajući u vidu tehničke i finansijske kapacitete definišu se realni, merljivi rokovi za dostizanje cilja: ciklus redovne zamene vodomera kako bi u upotrebi na mreži bili samo vodomeri kojima nije istekla važnost žiga od 5 godina.

U aktivnosti učestvuju zainteresovana JKP ViK, privredni subjekti i druga pravna lica, kao i organi nadležni za izradu i donošenje metroloških propisa i praćenje njihovog sprovođenja.

Glavne reči: Vodomeri, zakonska regulativa, vanredno overavanje vodomera

WATER METERS FOR COLD WATER - INHERITED PRACTICE OF WATER METER VERIFICATION AND THE POSSIBILITY OF COMPLIANCE WITH THE NEW LEGISLATION

Summary:

The paper presents the activities of the UTVSI related to the implementation of the Regulation on the Verification of Water Meters for Use in Households, Business Premises and Light Industry, which has been in force since January 1, 2026. The state of extraordinary verification of water meters in use within PUCs was analyzed, along with various limitations and obstacles to the strict enforcement of legal regulations. The goal is to analyze the actual situation, while respecting the regulations, and to come up with acceptable solutions, both for PUCs ViK and for the Directorate for Measures and Precious Metals - the administrative body responsible for metrology

Napomena: Ceo rad će biti objavljen u narednim brojevima časopisa Voda i sanitarna tehnika

and supervision of the implementation of the Law on Metrology. By reviewing the condition of water meters in several PUCs, taking into account technical and financial capacities, realistic, measurable deadlines for achieving the goal are defined: a cycle of regular water meter replacement so that only water meters whose 5-year stamp has not expired are in use on the network.

Interested PUCs, business entities and other legal entities, as well as authorities responsible for the development and adoption of metrological regulations and monitoring their implementation, participate in the activity.

Keywords: Water meters, legal regulations, extraordinary verification of water meters